

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

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A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF VARIOUS FILM ADAPTATIONS OF THE CLASSIC ENGLISH NOVEL: WHERE DOES THE CLASSIC END AND HOLLYWOOD BEGIN?

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Abstract: *This article will provide a comparative analysis of such novels as Oscar Wilde's «The Picture of Dorian Gray», Jane Austen's «Pride and Prejudice», Louisa May Alcott's «Little Women» and their film adaptations.*

Key words: *screen adaptation, literary eras, books, Victorian era, novels, actors, plotline and writer.*

Introduction

English classics are like a melody, a symphony of the soul that touches the most delicate strings of our hearts. Music is made of notes as English classics are made of imagination. As we all know, English literature consists of 8 periods and today we pay more attention to the 5th and 6th periods and the film adaptations of many masterpieces of this era. Classic literature is timeless. Cinematic adaptations of these creations serve to provide a visual immersion into the past for the 21st century generation. People prefer to watch films based on books because, the writers who lived in that era were able to masterfully convey on paper the entire atmosphere, customs and morals of that time.

Dorian Gray: screen and soul

"The Picture of Dorian Gray" is one of Wilde's most successful works, which he wrote in just 2 weeks. It has been filmed in different countries of the world more than 30 times. The novel seems to be asking to be filmed. The first screen version of the novel was released in 1915 by director Matt Moore and the latest version in 2009 by director Oliver Parker who filmed two more famous works by Wilde such as "An Ideal Husband" and "The Importance of Being Earnest". The plot of the novel is simple; an artist named Basil paints a portrait of a young man named Dorian Gray. The sitter makes a wish; he wants the painting to age for him, and he sells his soul for it. The portrait takes on all the dirt of his current life while he remains young and beautiful. The author himself said that, everyone sees their own sins and vices in his hero. So, if we compare the later version, then seemingly insignificant details change in it, for example, the portrait of Dorian Gray does not just age, but crawls with

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worms and rats. Lord Henry does not infect the main character with thoughts that life is short and art is eternal, but literally brings the young man to drinking establishments, thereby beginning the fatal fall to the bottom. The choice of actor for the main character was quite good. Dorian was played by Ben Barnes. Of course, the actor did not correspond to the description of the main character in the original source, after all, an angelic blond with golden curls and light eyes may be great, but not everyone likes it. The actor masterfully managed to get used to the role of his character, attracting many viewers. In general, the film managed to cope well with acting, costumes, dialogues. Yes, some scenes were added, deleted and changed, but this cannot be an excuse not to watch. And the film also, very well describes how a person idealizes the one he loves and finally loves not the person himself but the image. This can be seen in the scene where Dorian leaves his beloved after her theatrical failure, declaring that she has killed his love for her. After this, the girl commits suicide and this gives us a clear idea of what pride and egoism will lead to. Personally, the novel reminds me of Wilde's short story "Star Boy" in some ways. In general, this is a book about how aesthetics is connected with ethics and it can also be like an educational novel, making it clear that life for pleasure destroys personality.

"Little Women: Sisterhood and Growing Up". "Little Women" is a novel about four sisters growing up against the backdrop of war. They always wanted to remain the same carefree children as they are now, but no matter how hard they try to postpone their growing up, they are already women. Each goes through their own path of growing up under the influence of different events. At the moment, there are 9 film adaptations of the novel. The three most recent of them are those filmed in 1994, 2017 and 2019 years. It is very difficult to watch 4 sisters on the screen at once, so in the 2019 film adaptation, director Greta Gerwig reworked the classic plot of the story, turning it into a non-linear chronology, that is, the events of the film do not follow one after another, not like in the book, according to the logic of the plot. Different time periods follow each other showing how the sisters' situation changes at different periods of their lives. Because of this, in the first half of the film it will be a little difficult to catch this logic and connect the picture in your head. Personally, I liked how they used a warm light palette for the childhood shots; the coziness of the fireplace, Christmas breakfasts, and then the tone of adult life - in the cold. The cast of the film is simply magnificent, the role of the elder sister Margaret went to the charming actress Emma Watson, the soundtracks are simply wonderful and another undoubted plus of the film is the unique recreation of America in the middle of the 19th century, a cozy place called "New England". Both versions show that at that

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time a woman was considered a shallow person without a man and the key to a good life for women was a successful marriage, but still the work ended with a traditional happy ending.

"Pride and Prejudice: Love, Lies, and the Silver Screen". As we all know this masterpiece of Jane Austen "Pride and Prejudice" has conquered millions of hearts and it is popular not only with readers but also with filmmakers. If we give the shortest summary, then this is the story of Elizabeth Bennet a girl from an impoverished family, whose happiness and well-being depends on how well she marries. When the mysterious and rich Mr. Darcy moves into the neighboring estate, she becomes interested in him. But they both cannot understand and admit their feelings because of excessive pride and strong prejudice. "I would easily forgive his pride if he had not insulted mine..." Elizabeth Bennett's words about Mr. Darcy. Since 1938, at least 17 films have been made, not counting sequels. The most successful of them is considered to be the mini-series consisting of 6 episodes directed by Simon Langton. It is considered by viewers to be the best not only because of the choice and performance of the actors. In this film, everything seems to have come from the pages of the novel: magnificent costumes, luxurious interiors, landscapes of old rural England, love affairs and romantic feelings. And the 2005 film adaptation became much discussed among critics. They stated that the characters' personalities have nothing in common with the characters on the screen, only their names. There is no spirit of the era at all. The film may appeal to very young girls who do not burden themselves with reading the classics. Well, as for me, the 2005 film is also a wonderful film about love, shot with love. Especially the star of "Pirates of the Caribbean" Kira Knightley played Elizabeth Bennett superbly. It is important to note that no film can compare to the book, in terms of the volume of the characters.

Conclusion: In conclusion, I want to say that the greatest castles of feelings and ideas are built on the bricks of imagination. Every literary work is worthy of being read for centuries. For those who value the original book too much, there may not be an ideal film adaptation. Film adaptation of any work, no matter whether it turns out well or not, is already a great respect for the author and his/her work. Watching movies or TV series based on books is a cultural and spiritual relaxation for all of us!

References:

1. Wilde, O. (1890). *The Picture of Dorian Gray*. Lippincott's Monthly Magazine.
2. Alcott, L. M. (1868). *Little Women*. Roberts Brothers.
3. Austen, J. (1813). *Pride and Prejudice*. T. Egerton.
4. ReadRate. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://readrate.com>
5. Briefly. (n.d.). *Pride and Prejudice* by Jane Austen (summary). Retrieved from https://briefly.ru/ostin/gordost_i_predubezhdenie